

COMPLEX FORMATION OF URANYL ION WITH *o*-CRESOTIC ACID :
POTENTIOMETRIC, COLORIMETRIC AND
CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDY

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Like salicylic acid, *o*-cresotic acid also forms complex with uranyl ion. The formation of a red-coloured complex containing uranyl and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 molar ratio at about pH 4.5 is demonstrated by the inflection, break and maximum in colorimeter reading at one equivalent of alkali in all the potentiometric, conductometric and colorimetric titration curves of different mixtures of uranyl nitrate and monosodium *o*-cresotate.

Courtois (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1923, 33, 176) has shown the formation of a yellow-orange compound $[C_6H_4(OH)CO_2]UO_2$ with salicylic acid. Weinland and Hager (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 160, 193) have prepared many uranyl compounds with salicylic acid and bases. St. Weil and St. Rozenblum (*Bull. Trans. Inst. Pharm.*, Poland, 1902, 1, 1) obtained uranyl salicylate, $(C_6H_4.OH.CO_2)_2UO_2.H_2O$, from salicylic acid and uranyl acetate in hot aqueous solution in small needles of orange-rose colour. Anderson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 909) have studied the complex formation of uranyl ion with sulphosalicylic acid spectrophotometrically by Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113). Singh (D. Phil. Thesis, 1956, Allahabad University) has studied the uranyl sulphosalicylate and uranyl chloromercurisulphosalicylate complexes potentiometrically, conductometrically and colorimetrically.

Repman (*Lab. Prakt.*, U. S. S. R., 1941, 16, 27) has suggested that disodium salt of 5-cresotic acid reacts with uranyl acetate to form a coloured compound which can be used as an indicator for the analysis of phosphates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of uranyl nitrate were prepared by direct weighing of Baker's analysed sample of uranyl nitrate, $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. Uranium content was estimated gravimetrically (Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", London, 1951, p. 471).

The monosodium salt of *o*-cresotic acid was prepared by addition of an equivalent amount of A.R.-E. Merck sample of sodium bicarbonate in L.R.-B.D.H. sample of *o*-cresotic acid. The mother-liquor was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The crude sample of monosodium salt of *o*-cresotic acid was crystallised in absolute alcohol in white shining crystals and dried in a desiccator. Carbon, hydrogen and oxygen contents were determined by combustion. Standard solutions of monosodium *o*-cresotate were prepared by direct weighing of the prepared sample.

All the measurements were made at a constant temperature of $32^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. pH and conductivity measurements were made as described by Singh and Prakash (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 197). Colorimetric measurements were made with a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter, using colour filters Ks 42 and Ks 54 within the transmission ranges of 440 - 450 $m\mu$ and 500 - 560 $m\mu$ respectively.

Complex-forming Systems.—To study the complex formation of uranyl ion with monosodium *o*-cresotate, the monovariant method was used. To constant volumes of uranyl nitrate varying amounts of monosodium *o*-cresotate were added. Thus, a number of sets of mixtures containing uranyl nitrate and monosodium *o*-cresotate in the ratios 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 were prepared. To these mixtures varying amounts of standard solutions of caustic soda were added. The total volume of the mixture was kept constant in each case. The sets were left for about 24 hours to attain the equilibrium. For colorimetric measurements, solutions in which precipitation had taken place, were centrifuged to obtain clear solutions.

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

In the graph the abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali added per gram ion of hydrogen of the ligand, while the ordinate represents the measurements of the physical properties, viz., p_H , sp. conductivity and colorimetric readings.

Fig. 1 represents the changes in hydrogen-ion concentration of monosodium *o*-cresotate by the addition of uranyl nitrate. The p_H of monosodium *o*-cresotate

FIG. 2

(6.8) decreases by the addition of uranyl nitrate and becomes nearly constant after about one equivalent of uranyl nitrate. Curve A' shows p_n of only uranyl nitrate at similar concentrations. The curve A lies below A', indicating that there is an increase in hydrogen-ion concentration in the mixtures, which is only possible by the displacement of hydroxyl hydrogen during the complex formation. In Fig. 1, when the colorimetric measurements with filter Ks 42 within the transmission range of 400–450 $m\mu$ are plotted against the volume of uranyl nitrate, from the curve it is clear that the increase in colour becomes almost constant when one equivalent of uranyl nitrate is added to the monosodium *o*-cresotate solution. It indicates the formation of 1:1 complex with uranyl ion and *o*-cresotate.

Fig. 2 shows the variation of hydrogen-ion concentration with the progressive addition of alkali to the systems (i) (0.0333*M*) uranyl nitrate (curve A) and mixtures of (0.0333*M*) uranyl nitrate and (0.0333*M*) monosodium *o*-cresotate mixed in the ratios of 1:1 (curve B), 1:2 (curve C), 1:3 (curve D), while the curve E shows the reaction of alkali on monosodium *o*-cresotate itself.

When uranyl nitrate is titrated with alkali, the precipitation of uranyl hydroxide takes place when about two equivalents of alkali have been added (Fig. 1, curve A). The reaction may be represented as :

Curve E in Fig. 1 represents the blank experiment for comparison. It indicates the variation of p_n of monosodium *o*-cresotate solution on further addition of alkali.

When the two reactants are mixed in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 ratios, a reddish white precipitate appears in the mixtures, supernatant liquid being light red. The precipitate dissolves in alkali above p_n 4.15, the colour of the mixture being deep red. Above p_n 6.05, the yellow precipitate of uranyl hydroxide starts precipitating and complete precipitation of uranyl hydroxide takes place at about p_n 8.2 after the addition of about two equivalents of alkali. From the curves B, C and D (Fig. 1) it is clear that there are two inflections in the curves B, C and D (Fig. 2), one at one equivalent and the other at two equivalents of alkali. The displaced hydroxyl hydrogen of monosodium *o*-cresotate is titrated by one equivalent of alkali and a red-coloured complex is formed containing uranyl ion and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio. This complex breaks up above p_n 6.05, and uranyl ion is completely precipitated by two equivalents of alkali, denoting the second inflection at two equivalents.

Similar observations were made in the case of specific conductivity study (Fig. 3). Specific conductivity was plotted against the equivalents of alkali. Curve A (Fig. 3) shows the conductometric titration of (0.0333*M*) uranyl nitrate with alkali. There is a definite break in the curve A, when about two equivalents of alkali have been added. The reaction can be represented by the equation, shown above.

Curve E in Fig. 3 represents the reaction of (0.0333*M*) monosodium *o*-cresotate by alkali. Due to absence of free hydrogen in the system and progressive addition of alkali, a straight line is obtained.

The curves B, C and D (Fig. 3) show the conductometric titrations of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures of (0.0333*M*) uranyl nitrate and (0.0333*M*) monosodium

o-cresotate. The curve B shows that specific conductivity decreases by the addition of alkali up to about one equivalent of alkali and then increases showing a break

FIG. 3

at one equivalent. The break at one equivalent of alkali shows the formation of an 1:1 complex in which complex formation takes place by oxygen atoms of the hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. Due to an excess of monosodium *o*-cresotale in the system, the specific conductivity curves C and D of 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures do not show break at exactly one equivalent of alkali.

Colorimeter readings of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures of (0.0333*M*) uranyl nitrate and (0.0333*M*) monosodium *o*-cresotale show interesting results (Fig. 4). Monosodium *o*-cresotale being colorless gives zero reading and uranyl nitrate also does not show much change on the colorimeter scale. By the addition of alkali the colorimeter readings in all the mixtures increase and reach at a maximum value when one equivalent of alkali is added in all the mixtures at about pH 4.5, the colour of the solution being dark red. On further addition of alkali, the colorimeter readings decrease and finally uranyl hydroxide is precipitated completely from the complex. This also shows the formation of the above mentioned 1:1 complex of uranyl ion and *o*-cresotale.

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